

Turbulent Isopycnal Mixing dominates Thermohaline Transformations of Intermediate Ocean Waters

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The ocean, because of its ability to store heat and as the biggest mediator of water exchanges on Earth, modulates the climate from years to centuries. By combining Water Mass transformation and the Temporal-Residual-Mean frameworks, together with a direct estimation of turbulent diffusivity (computed through an artificial intelligence method), we determine temperature and salinity transformations along density surfaces. Because isopycnal transformations barely alter the density field, they remain hidden from the ocean dynamics. Here we unveil these hidden, isopycnal transformations from *in situ* observations at 1,000-m depth. We shows that these isopycnal transformations are 5 times as large as their diapycnal counterpart and are occurring for $\sim 67\%$ in the Southern Ocean. Our estimations stress the role of the spatially-varying and anisotropic characteristics of isopycnal diffusion, often not considered in ocean models. This has major consequences for our understanding of the role of the ocean in response to anthropogenic climate changes.

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20 Ocean circulation transports a vast amount of water over the globe (up to 150 Sv, where
21 $1 \text{ Sv} \equiv 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, in the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, for instance)¹. This large-scale ocean cir-
22 culation is also associated with transport of heat (up to 1.5 PW northward at 20°N)² and freshwater
23 (around 0.5 Sv southward at 35°N in the North Atlantic)³. The former is a fundamental component
24 of the climate equilibrium and adjustment by transporting the excess of heat from the tropics to the
25 poles; whereas the latter indirectly reflects the geographical pattern of evaporation, precipitation,
26 river discharge, and ice melting, all taking part in the water cycle. In particular, the ocean is the
27 most important region of precipitation and evaporation (i.e., 75% and 85%, respectively), making
28 it particularly relevant for the Earth water cycle⁴.

29 Beyond this equilibrated view, the Earth is experiencing changes since the pre-industrial
30 era, with a significant amount of anthropogenically-induced greenhouse gases released into the
31 atmosphere⁵. As a consequence, the surface atmospheric temperature is increasing⁵, despite a
32 significant mitigation by the ocean, with an ocean absorption of about 90% of the Earth's heat
33 excess⁵⁻⁷. Together with this warming, the water cycle is also affected⁸. This is reflected by
34 changes in the evaporation and precipitation patterns and amplitudes⁵. These changes, either
35 directly (when over the ocean) or indirectly through runoffs (when over land), are imprinted
36 in the ocean freshwater transport^{9,10} through, for instance, modification of the ocean salinity
37 distribution¹¹. Hence, the ocean heat and freshwater transports are central actors of the Earth
38 equilibrium and climate changes.

39 Mesoscale eddies are ubiquitous worldwide in the ocean¹² and, unlike the mean transport,

40 they contribute to the heat and freshwater transport in two folds. Firstly, equivalently to the lami-
41 nar component, they move ocean water properties (i.e., its temperature and salinity) in a conserv-
42 ing manner within the ocean. Secondly, eddies also induce a transformation of these properties
43 through turbulent diffusion¹³ (e.g., mixing cold and warm waters or salty and fresh ones). Trans-
44 formations of seawater properties can occur either through interactions with the atmosphere at the
45 ocean surface or through turbulent diffusion in the ocean interior. Whereas the former is easier to
46 estimate^{8,14}, the latter has always been more difficult to assess and is often deduced using inverse
47 methodology¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Assessing the role of turbulent eddy diffusion for heat and freshwater trans-
48 ports and for the transformation of seawater properties is a timely question of ocean and climate
49 sciences, as demonstrated by numerous numerical model studies¹⁹⁻²¹.

50 There has been a large range of studies on Water Mass Transformations²²⁻²⁸. These studies
51 often assess the transformations in term of temperature and salinity changes, without specifically
52 separating the respective role of isopycnal and diapycnal transformations. In parallel, the role
53 of diapycnal diffusion on temperature and salinity transformations in the ocean interior has been
54 well established^{16,29}. More recently, studies have suggested the key role of isopycnal processes
55 on heat and freshwater uptakes^{30,31}, opening the possibility of an important role of the isopycnal
56 diffusion. This has been further confirmed as potentially important in the North Atlantic for the
57 maintenance of the mean temperature and salinity structure³². However these studies rely on either
58 numerical models or inverse methods, both intrinsically depending on a chosen closure scheme
59 (and sometimes imposed parameters). Hence it is key to use direct observations to assess whether
60 isopycnal or diapycnal diffusion is dominant in the ocean interior. Indeed, in ocean science where

61 reproducible controlled experiments are not possible, the use of direct observations is the only way
62 to validate or invalidate hypotheses derived from these numerical or inverse modeling approaches.

63 In this work, we use direct observations to assess the changes and transformations of tem-
64 perature and salinity induced by mesoscale eddy turbulence, which acts as an equivalent isopycnal
65 turbulent diffusion. We shows that, at 1,000-m depth, these temperature and salinity changes
66 mainly occurred in the Southern Ocean and along the Gulf Stream. These isopycnal changes in-
67 duces temperature and salinity transformations significantly more important than their diapycnal
68 equivalents. We also conclude that the spatially-variable and anisotropic natures of the isopycnal
69 turbulent diffusion are keys for an accurate estimation of the temperature and salinity transforma-
70 tions.

71 **Results**

72 The major difficulty of obtaining robust, direct estimations of heat and freshwater transforma-
73 tions by eddies comes from the need of knowing turbulent diffusive coefficients independently of
74 temperature and salinity fields (to avoid the dependence of the results to a closure scheme)^{33,34}.
75 Here, to circumvent this difficulty, we have used the recently estimated diffusivity coefficients³⁵
76 derived from Argo float deep displacements³⁶. This dataset has been obtained using a class of
77 data driven Artificial Intelligence methods: the Analog Method^{37,38}. There, the spatially-varying
78 and anisotropic diffusivity coefficients were estimated through local tracer dispersion induced by
79 a turbulent velocity field reconstructed from deep Argo displacements. This dataset provides the

80 full diffusivity tensor, explicitly acknowledging the anisotropy, rather than a single diffusivity co-
81 efficient, as most commonly done^{33,34,39}. These resulting diffusivity coefficients are strong where
82 the flow is strong (Fig. 1d and e), but with a slight spatial-offset with the core of the currents^{40,41},
83 hence with the largest density gradients. This could be rationalized by the existence of Kinetic
84 Energy transfers⁴². These coefficients (Fig. 1d and e) together with temperature and salinity fields
85 from gridded ISAS17 product⁴³ (Optimal Interpolation⁴⁴ from Argo profiles, Fig. 1a and b) allow
86 us to have a direct estimation of isopycnal heat and freshwater transformations and uncover an
87 unobserved facet of deep ocean circulation.

88 **Effect of Isopycnal Turbulent Diffusion.** In the present study we assess the global effect of the
89 turbulent diffusion on temperature and salinity fields. However, because of observational con-
90 straints (i.e., the typical parking depth of Argo float deep displacements), our study focuses at
91 1,000-m depth. This depth is particularly relevant for estimating heat and freshwater transports
92 and seawater property transformations for two reasons. (1) It is close to the depth of the maximum
93 of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (depth of no-motion for this circulation, as es-
94 timated at 26.5°N in the North Atlantic by RAPID)⁴⁵. (2) It is the depth with largest contrast in
95 salinity^{46,47}, but also includes signatures of the coldest waters⁴⁷ (Fig. 1).

96 The transformation of seawater properties works hand in hand with the concept of Water
97 Masses⁴⁸. Water Masses are volumes of water with consistent seawater properties (Fig. 1f) that are
98 set through ocean-atmosphere exchange at the ocean surface where water masses originate. They
99 then spread within the ocean through advection and mixing and are transformed by the latter. At

100 1,000-m depth, we will consider three intermediate water masses: Red Sea–Persian Gulf Inter-
101 mediate Water (RSPGIW) formed in the Red Sea and Persian Gulf⁴⁹, the Mediterranean Water⁵⁰
102 (MW) reaching the Atlantic through the Strait of Gibraltar, and the AntArctic Intermediate Water⁵¹
103 (AAIW) intersecting the 1,000-m depth along the the Polar Front⁵². We will also consider more
104 dense Water Masses, namely the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), its transformed southern
105 extension, the Circumpolar Deep Water⁵³ (CDW), and the Antarctic Bottom Water⁵⁴ (AABW).
106 Despite not being their depth of maximum intrusion, these Water Masses are present at 1,000-m
107 depth in the high latitudes of the North Atlantic and of the Southern Ocean (Fig. 1f).

108 To estimate the impact of the turbulent diffusion on the temperature and salinity of these
109 water masses we follow the Temporal-Residual-Mean framework (see Methods – Isopycnal Tur-
110 bulent Transformation Framework)¹³. This framework disentangles advective and mixing effects
111 when eddy turbulence is averaged. This allows for an accurate attribution of eddy-induced trans-
112 port and transformation. Also, this framework acknowledges that transformations acts within
113 isopycnal layers as epineutral flux (Fig. 2). To this purpose averaging are done along-isopycnal,
114 so that fictitious diapycnal transport, due to incorrect estimates of the isopycnal slopes, can be
115 limited⁵⁵. This transformation-induced process has almost no signature on the density field (ex-
116 cept for the weak cabbeling and thermobaricity components, although they remain crucial for the
117 density transformations⁵⁶), nor pressure, nor circulation. As a consequence, there is no impact on
118 Potential Energy and it can act passively, as long as Eddy Kinetic Energy remains to maintain the
119 turbulent diffusion. In this sense, for the ocean dynamics, it remains hidden along the isopycnals
120 (Fig. 1c). However it still contributes to heat and freshwater transport from cold to warm and from

121 salty to fresh regions, respectively. This process can be described in the form of temperature and
122 salinity rates of change or of water-mass transformation rates (Methods – Water Mass Transfor-
123 mation Rates). The rates of change of a material property (temperature or salinity) measures the
124 amount of warming/cooling or salinification/freshening induced by the isopycnal turbulent diffu-
125 sion; whereas the transformation accounts for the amount of seawater that have their properties
126 transformed by this process.

127 **Rates of temperature and salinity change.** As mentioned above, the isopycnal diffusion of tem-
128 perature and salinity can be assessed as the induced rates of change in terms of temperature and
129 salinity [Methods – (10)]. High magnitudes of the rates of change are due to high diffusivity co-
130 efficients, sharp isopycnal temperature or salinity gradients, or a combination of both. At 1,000-m
131 depth, we find that they are of the order of kelvins per year or tenth of (g kg^{-1}) per year [or a
132 few 10^{-8} K s^{-1} and $10^{-9} \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$] for temperature and salinity, respectively. These rates of
133 change are mainly located in the Southern Ocean, along the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, and,
134 to a lesser extent, in the North West of the North Atlantic (Fig. 3a and 4a). Indeed the Southern
135 Ocean account for 67% of the global rates of change for temperature and salinity [as measured by
136 the R^2 of the transformations described in (11)], despite representing only 31% of the global ocean
137 area. When including North Atlantic it reaches 95% for temperature and salinity rates of change.
138 A local maximum of these rates of change can be seen in the Zapiola gyre, which corresponds to a
139 local maximum of diffusivity coefficients (Fig. 1d and e). There is also significant rates of change
140 along the Agulhas return current and its merging with the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, which
141 also corresponds to a local maximum of diffusivity coefficients. Indeed, between South Africa and

142 the Kerguelen plateau, there is a warming and salinification of the relatively cold and salty AAIW
143 (Fig. 3a and 4a), a cooling and freshening of the relatively warm and fresh AAIW, and a warming
144 and salinification of the warm and salty residual of RSGPIW (trapped in the Agulhas system⁵⁷,
145 Fig. 1b).

146 Unlike the geographical map that reveals where the rates of change are located, the TS-
147 diagram (i.e., representation with temperature-salinity axes) reveals which water masses are sub-
148 jected to the isopycnal diffusion (i.e., change along isopycnal surfaces). This can be represented
149 globally (insets in Fig. 3a and 4a), or displayed for each relevant basin (following the division of
150 Fig. 1f), which allows a simpler relation with local Water Masses (Fig. 3b-e and 4b-e). In the
151 North Atlantic, despite the weak isopycnal turbulent diffusion coefficients in the subtropical gyre
152 interior (Fig. 1d and e), temperature and salinity rates of change within the MW (along the 27.6-
153 27.8 kg m⁻³ density class) are visible with a slight cooling and a freshening of MW (Fig. 3b). A
154 more important cooling and freshening is also visible at the edge between MW and NADW. In the
155 Southern Ocean the geographical separation is quite revealing. It suggests different water masses
156 at play for each of the three sectors (Atlantic, Indian, and Pacific). In the Atlantic sector of the
157 Southern Ocean, we observe a cooling and freshening of CDW and a warming and salinification
158 of AAIW and AABW (Fig. 3c and 4c). In the Indian and Pacific sectors, the rates of change
159 correspond to a warming and salinification of the AABW, a cooling and freshening of the CDW,
160 a warming and salinification of the coldest and freshest portion of the AAIW, and a cooling and
161 freshening of the warmest and saltiest portion of the AAIW (Fig. 3d and e and 4d and e). In the
162 Indian sector, there is also a warming and salinification of the warmer portion of the AAIW, which

163 derives from RSPGIW⁵⁷.

164 **Water Mass Transformations.** To further quantify these effects, the isopycnal turbulent diffu-
165 sion can also be expressed as Water Masses Transformation (see Methods – Water Mass Trans-
166 formation Rates). As discussed earlier, since the turbulent eddy-induced diffusion acts along
167 isopycnals¹³ it cannot modify density (except for weak nonlinear effects, which affect density
168 and hence the circulation)⁵⁶. Hence we will focus on transformations induced by temperature and
169 salinity changes. We use the traditional Water Mass Transformation framework^{48,58}, often defined
170 across density layers. Here, we compute transformation rates induced by temperature and salinity
171 changes along the isopycnals [see Methods – (11)]. They are computed both globally and for each
172 region defined earlier (Fig. 1f). These two transformations are evidences of heat and freshwater
173 transport by isopycnal turbulent diffusion.

174 We find density transformations of the order of ± 2 Sv (i.e., density-class standard deviation)
175 for density changes induced by either temperature and salinity, respectively (colored – red and blue
176 – bars in Fig. 5a and c, respectively). This is important as these transformations correspond to a 70-
177 m layer only (i.e., the typical density layer thickness due to the stratification at our studied depth,
178 see Method – Water Mass Transformation Rates and Supplementary Fig. 1). For comparison, the
179 buoyancy transformations are of the order of a few tens of Sverdrup when computed over the full
180 ocean depth⁵⁶. We rationalize the importance of the temperature and salinity transformations over
181 the density ones because of their strong thermohaline compensating effect on density (i.e., the so
182 called spiciness). The Water Masses located at our studied depth exhibit particularly intense spici-

183 ness contrasts¹⁸, although it is not necessarily the case at other depths. More broadly, at the ocean
184 surface, warming regions are often regions of net evaporation, whereas cooling regions are often
185 regions of net precipitation. This means that there is a non-negligible part of the ocean circulation
186 that transports heat and freshwater from cold and fresh regions to warm and salty regions without
187 transporting density.

188 For reference, we compare these isopycnal transformations to the diapycnal ones, which in-
189 duce a net density transformations⁵⁶. These diapycnal transformations are computed using recon-
190 structed vertical diffusion coefficients^{59,60} (see Methods – Alternative Diffusivity Coefficients.),
191 which show the expected typical control by topography (Supplementary Fig. 2). To compare the
192 isopycnal and diapycnal transformations we measure their amplitude through their standard devi-
193 ation along the density coordinate. We find that the temperature and salinity isopycnal transfor-
194 mations are 3 and 5 times as large as the diapycnal ones (black vs cyan line in Fig. 5a and b),
195 respectively. Note that this result contrasts with density transformations for which, as expected,
196 diapycnal transformations is the dominant factor over isopycnal ones, except for a few specific
197 Water Masses (i.e., Subantarctic Mode Water and AAIW, and CDW), for which cabbeling and
198 thermobaricity are important factors⁵⁶.

199 These dominant isopycnal transformations reveal a mean density gain and loss of +1.5 Sv
200 and -1.9 Sv, respectively. The density transformations correspond to three regimes in density
201 coordinates (Fig. 5): a warming and salinification of the lightest water, a cooling and freshening
202 of density classes between 27.35 and 28 kg m⁻³, and a warming and salinification of the densest

203 water. As expected within an isopycnal framework, transformations with respect to neutral density
204 classes show that density gain and loss by cooling and warming are associated to density loss and
205 gain by freshening and salinification, respectively, preserving the density field (Fig. 5e). Looking
206 at water classes and regional separation, we find warming and salinification of the lightest class of
207 AAIW and cooling of the densest class of AAIW. This mainly occurs in the Indian sector of the
208 Southern Ocean. On the other hand, transformations associated with CDW and AABW exhibit a
209 warming and salinification, which mainly occurred in the Atlantic sector of the Southern Ocean,
210 and to a second degree in the Pacific sector for CDW. A transformation peak is also visible in the
211 North Atlantic sector. It corresponds to a cooling compensated by a freshening at the edge between
212 MW and NADW. Similarly, in the same sector, the full range of MW is also transformed through
213 cooling and freshening, whereas a slight warming and salinification also occurs for the NADW.

214 To better understand the role and to assess the importance of spatially-varying anisotropic
215 diffusivity coefficients³⁶, we have tested a range of less complex diffusivity coefficients (see Meth-
216 ods – Alternative Diffusivity Coefficients). To quantitatively test the mis-estimations of these
217 simplest diffusivity coefficients we used their relative error in comparison to the most complete
218 version [see Methods – (12)]. The simplest one was a spatially-uniform and isotropic isopycnal
219 diffusivity coefficients (light gray bars in Fig. 5a and b) mainly preserves the signs of the trans-
220 formations, but underestimate them by up to 53% for both temperature and salinity. Nonetheless
221 this approximation warm and salinified AAIW from 27.4 kg m^{-3} to 27.5 kg m^{-3} , whereas it was
222 cool and freshen with the most complete version of the diffusivity. Using spatially-varying and
223 isotropic isopycnal diffusivity coefficients (dark gray bars in Fig. 5a and b) better conserves the

224 shape of the transformations but overestimates by up to 48% the temperature and salinity rates of
225 change, respectively.

226 **Robustness of the Isopycnal Diffusivity Dataset.** To test the robustness of our results, we have
227 recomputed the temperature and salinity transformations using two alternative diffusivity coeffi-
228 cient datasets (see Methods – Alternative Diffusivity Coefficients). The first dataset, that we named
229 Groeskamp, estimates diffusivity using salinity observations and assuming the validity of the mix-
230 ing length theory³⁴. The second dataset, that we named Roach, uses the same deep Argo float
231 displacements than us, but a different methodology: a pairwise dispersion³⁹.

232 Groeskamp and Roach diffusivities (Fig. 6a and b, respectively) have the same overall pattern
233 than our reference diffusivities (Fig. 1d and e): intensification in western boundary currents and
234 within the Antarctic Circumpolar Current. Because Groeskamp and Roach diffusivity coefficients
235 correspond solely to the cross flow diffusion, they are more comparable to our secondary diffusiv-
236 ity coefficients (Fig. 1e), which are by construction weaker than the primary ones. Groeskamp and
237 Roach diffusivity coefficients range between $2,000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $5,000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in active regions (as
238 our secondary diffusivity coefficients). In comparison with the two other datasets, Roach diffusiv-
239 ity coefficients are less spatially-smooth.

240 Because Groeskamp and Roach datasets provide only a single local diffusivity coefficient,
241 we restrict the comparison to the spatially-varying and isotropic framework. Computing the tem-
242 perature and salinity transformations with the different diffusivity coefficient datasets show the
243 good consistency of the results (Fig. 6c and d). When using our spatially-varying and isotropic

244 diffusivity coefficients, we find stronger transformations than those obtained with Groeskamp and
245 Roach diffusivity coefficients. However the transformations are qualitatively well represented. As
246 expected, the agreement is better when applying the spatially-varying and isotropic diffusivity co-
247 efficients solely based on the secondary diffusivity coefficients. Here the agreement is qualitative
248 and quantitative. This stresses the robustness of our described temperature and salinity transfor-
249 mations with respect to the methodology used to infer the diffusivity coefficients.

250 **Discussion**

251 The ocean, through its absorption of 91% of the heat imbalance⁵ and as the largest region of
252 evaporation and precipitation on Earth⁴, is a key component of our changing climate. At first
253 glance, ocean is filled by fast, intense mesoscale eddy features, ubiquitous worldwide¹². Hence the
254 role of these eddies and their associated turbulence in balancing the ocean circulation and its heat
255 and freshwater transports remains a vivid question of current climate and ocean research.

256 This question is even more intriguing when acknowledging that, since eddy turbulence corre-
257 sponds to a flow along isopycnals, its induced mixing cannot modify density (except through weak
258 – but potentially locally important⁵⁶ – nonlinear effects), hence the circulation. However, they
259 interact with temperature and salinity fields, transforming seawater properties along their way¹³,
260 without trace on the circulation, but still acting on the heat and freshwater transports. From an
261 energetic point-of-view, by transporting temperature and salinity properties, without disturbing the
262 density (because of compensating effect), these transformations do not impact the potential energy,

263 remaining hidden for ocean dynamics and acting passively, as long as Eddy Kinetic Energy exists
264 for maintaining the eddy turbulence.

265 The first result of the present study is the observational-estimation of temperature and salin-
266 ity transformations at 1 000-m depth. By using observations of the ocean temperature and salin-
267 ity together with a direct observational estimate of anisotropic diffusivity coefficients induced by
268 mesoscale eddy turbulence³⁶, we have unveiled the existence of this intense, hidden isopycnal
269 transformations fundamental for the transport of heat and freshwater in the ocean and, therefore,
270 for setting the global temperature and salinity seawater properties. These isopycnal transformations
271 are 3 and 5 times as large as the more classical diapycnal transformations in terms of temperature
272 and salinity transformations, respectively. In particular, in the North Atlantic we find an important
273 dominance of isopycnal transformations over diapycnal transformations at our studied, 1,000-m
274 depth, consistently with an independent recent observational study⁶¹. We have shown that these
275 dominant isopycnal transformations occur for $\sim 67\%$ in the Southern Ocean (despite representing
276 only 31% of the global ocean area) and is particularly relevant for AAIW, CDW, and AABW.

277 The second result is the demonstration of the importance of acknowledging the full com-
278 plexity of the isopycnal diffusivity tensor. We have shown that considering the spatially-varying
279 and anisotropic diffusivity coefficients is key for the accurate transformation estimations. Simpler
280 diffusivity coefficients (as often used in parameterization of laminar/eddy-less ocean component
281 used in some current climate models)⁶² lead to misestimation of the seawater properties transfor-
282 mation (by up to 53%), thus impacting oceanic heat and freshwater transports. Although, because

283 our study is limited to a single-depth layer, we could not quantitatively estimate these impacts.
284 Hence, this should be tested in state-of-the-art climate models to further identify the relevance and
285 significance of our finding. In particular, the role of spatially-varying and anisotropic diffusiv-
286 ity coefficients in modulating and redistributing ocean heat storage in climate simulations should
287 be evaluated. Given the projected changes of ocean mesoscale turbulence over the 21st century⁶³,
288 hence of the isopycnal diffusivity coefficients³⁶, the future response of our identified intense hidden
289 isopycnal transformations is in question.

290 Whereas, the role of diathermal and diahaline water-mass transformations has been long
291 established^{16,29}, there exists in the recent literature evidence of the importance of the isopycnal
292 direction over the diapycnal one for these temperature and salinity transformations^{18,32,61}. Our
293 direct estimates suggest the dominance of isopycnal diffusion over diapycnal diffusion at 1,000-m
294 depth. We hypothesize that this is because we fully acknowledged the anisotropic nature of the
295 isopycnal diffusion within our framework, unlike in inverse or numerical modeling studies. This
296 dominance is particularly important since isopycnal transformations are key for heat uptake in the
297 context of Global Warming³⁰.

298 Because of observational constraints³⁶, our analysis is restricted at 1,000-m depth. Hence our
299 results are only representative of an horizontal slice of the ocean, potentially masking geographical
300 variations linked to the local layer thickness (relatively more important in the Southern Ocean
301 and in the subpolar North Atlantic). However, this depth is particularly interesting because it
302 is close to the depth of the maximum meridional overturning transport in the Atlantic (i.e., the

303 depth of no-motion for this circulation) and it is where some of the most saline waters reside
304 and where the coldest waters also exist. This makes this depth particularly relevant for heat and
305 freshwater transports. However, given the intensity of the circulation and transformation identified
306 in our study, it is important to acknowledge it at other depths. In particular, diapycnal mixing
307 could become more prevalent near the seabed, mitigating the key role of isopycnal mixing for
308 temperature and salinity transformations. Hence, building a robust 3-dimensional picture, fully
309 constrained by observations, of the isopycnal turbulent transformations of the global ocean will be
310 a direction for future work.

311 **Methods**

312 **Isopycnal Turbulent Transformation Framework.** Starting from the advection equation for a
313 tracer (which could be temperature or salinity) away from forcing (mainly occurring at the ocean
314 surface) and for high Péclet number ($Pe \gg 1$, measuring the advection to diffusion ratio), we have:

$$D_t C = 0, \tag{1}$$

315 where C is the tracer concentration and D_t is the material derivative ($=\partial_t + u\partial_x + v\partial_y + w\partial_z$, where
316 t is time, x , y and z are the zonal, meridional, and vertical coordinates, and u , v , and w are the
317 zonal, meridional, and vertical velocities).

318 This equation can be modified to show the evolution of the large-spatial scale or long-time
319 scale by splitting each terms in an Eulerian mean ($\bar{\cdot}$) and its associated anomaly (\cdot'). This reads:

$$\overline{D}_t \bar{C} = -\partial_x \overline{u' C'} - \partial_y \overline{v' C'} - \partial_z \overline{w' C'}, \quad (2)$$

320 where \overline{D}_t is the mean material derivative ($=\partial_t + \bar{u}\partial_x + \bar{v}\partial_y + \bar{w}\partial_z$).

321 This shows that several mean (\bar{C} , \bar{u} , \bar{v} , and \bar{w}) and turbulent ($\overline{u' C'}$, $\overline{v' C'}$, and $\overline{w' C'}$) terms
 322 contribute to the maintenance of the mean state. In this context, we can redistribute the terms^{13,64}
 323 so that the evolution of the tracer becomes:

$$\widehat{D}_t \hat{C} = d_{\hat{C}}, \quad (3)$$

324 where \hat{C} is the modified tracer, \widehat{D}_t is the modified material derivative [$=\partial_t + \hat{u}\partial_x + \hat{v}\partial_y + \hat{w}\partial_z$, and
 325 $\hat{u}=\bar{u}+\tilde{u}$, $\hat{v}=\bar{v}+\tilde{v}$, and $\hat{w}=\bar{w}+\tilde{w}$, where \tilde{u} , \tilde{v} , and \tilde{w} are the zonal, meridional and vertical eddy-
 326 induced velocities, respectively], and $d_{\hat{C}}$ is the transformation term. This expression suggests that
 327 the modified tracer is advected by both the mean and the eddy-induced velocity⁶⁵ and transformed.
 328 In this Temporal-Residual-Mean framework, the eddy-induced advection and the transformation
 329 are consequences of the skew-symmetric and symmetric components of the turbulent flux, respec-
 330 tively. This framework is particularly useful to accurately separate and attribute the advection and
 331 mixing effects of averaged eddy turbulence. The advection effect only displaces tracer properties,
 332 whereas the mixing effect changes tracer properties. Hence, this framework avoids the misinter-
 333 pretation of eddy-induced transport by horizontal turbulence as transformation.

334 In the ocean interior (i.e., below the ocean mixed layer), the transformation term can take the
 335 form⁵⁶ of

$$d_{\hat{C}} = d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{iso}} + d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{dia}}, \quad (4)$$

336 where $d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{iso}}$ and $d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{dia}}$ are the transformation along the isopycnal and the diapycnal direction. Here,
 337 by being in the ocean interior (i.e., below mixed layer depth), we have neglected the potential
 338 effect of horizontal transformation (important within the mixed layer). In the rest of the study,
 339 we will focus on the isopycnal component of these fluxes and compare it to the diapycnal one.
 340 Note that isopycnal heat and freshwater transformations act along constant density surface, thus,
 341 by construction they avoid density gradients. Although, the diapycnal component, induced by
 342 small-scale mixing processes⁶⁶, will be used as a reference. It is worth noting that the use horizon-
 343 tal diffusion instead of isopycnal diffusion outside of the mixed layer is fundamentally flawed⁵⁵.
 344 With this approximation, we would find transformations that are completely missing the correct
 345 warming/cooling freshening/salinification. Also, as expected for such flawed approximation, the
 346 compensation between temperature and salinity changes are missed. This would result in unreal-
 347 istic transformations.

348 Following a downgradient flux closure^{13,67} (i.e., Fick's law), the density-weighted isopycnal
 349 transformation reads:

$$d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{iso}} = \partial_z \gamma \nabla_n \cdot \left(\mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\nabla_n \hat{C}}{\partial_z \gamma} \right), \quad (5)$$

350 where ∇_n refers to gradient along the neutral density (γ) and \mathbf{K} is the, possibly spatially-varying,
 351 anisotropic diffusivity tensor acting along the neutral density (or anisotropic epineutral diffusivity

352 tensor). Here the gradient is computed using the projected nonorthogonal approach^{68,69}. The
 353 diffusivity tensor is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} \kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}} & \kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}} \\ \kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}} & \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

354 where \tilde{x} and \tilde{y} are the zonal and meridional direction along neutral density, respectively, and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}$,
 355 $\kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}$, and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}$ are the zonal, meridional, and cross diffusivities along the neutral density, respectively.
 356 Hence the isopycnal transformations for a spatially-varying and anisotropic diffusivity tensor read:

$$d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{iso}} = \partial_z \gamma \partial_{\tilde{x}} \left(\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \partial_{\tilde{x}} \hat{C} \right) + \partial_z \gamma \partial_{\tilde{x}} \left(\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \partial_{\tilde{y}} \hat{C} \right) + \partial_z \gamma \partial_{\tilde{y}} \left(\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \partial_{\tilde{x}} \hat{C} \right) + \partial_z \gamma \partial_{\tilde{y}} \left(\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \partial_{\tilde{y}} \hat{C} \right). \quad (7)$$

357 This expression shows that the diffusivity is dependent on 3 scalars that measured both the
 358 intensity of the diffusivity and its orientation. Indeed, since the off-diagonal term are strictly
 359 identical in (6), it simply induces a rotation of diffusivity, which will acts independently along its
 360 two orthogonal natural directions (directions after rotation). Here it becomes apparent that the use
 361 of a single coefficient cannot fully represent the complexity of this isopycnal transformations, both
 362 in term of intensity and directionality.

363 **Computation of Epineutral Flux.** One last difficulty is to estimate the gradient along neutral
 364 density⁶⁹ (or epineutral gradient) as expressed in (7): computing the ∇_n (or $\partial_{\tilde{x}}$ and $\partial_{\tilde{y}}$). As an

365 example, but it would be equivalent for the meridional direction, for the zonal direction, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\partial_{\tilde{x}}\sigma &\simeq \frac{\Delta\sigma|_{\gamma}}{\Delta\tilde{x}} \simeq \frac{\Delta\sigma|_z + \Delta\sigma|_x}{\sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \delta z^2}} \simeq \frac{\partial_x\sigma \Delta x + \partial_z\sigma \delta z}{\Delta x \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta z^2}{\Delta x^2}}}, \\
&\simeq \partial_x\sigma + s_x\partial_z\sigma - \frac{1}{2}s_x^2\partial_x\sigma - \frac{1}{2}s_x^3\partial_z\sigma + \dots, \\
&\simeq \partial_x\sigma + s_x\partial_z\sigma,
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

366 where σ is any scalar quantity (e.g., Temperature or Salinity), $s_x = \delta z / \Delta x$ is the zonal component
367 of the isopycnal slope, $\Delta\sigma|_{\{\gamma, x, z\}}$ is the difference in σ at constant γ , x , and z , respectively, $\Delta\tilde{x}$
368 is the distance at constant γ along the zonal direction, and Δx and δz are the zonal and vertical
369 distances, respectively, covered by the neutral density surface.

370 In the last calculation a few approximations have been done: (i) $\Delta\tilde{x} \simeq \sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \delta z^2}$, assum-
371 ing that the epineutral displacement can be geometrically approximated by the zonal and verti-
372 cal displacement; (ii) $\delta z \ll \Delta x$, assuming that the vertical displacement of the epineutral is weak
373 compared to the zonal one (i.e., small slope approximation⁶⁵) allowing a Taylor expansion of the
374 denominator; and (iii) $\partial_x\sigma$ and $\partial_z\sigma$ are constant over Δx and δz , respectively. Equivalently we
375 have $\partial_{\tilde{y}}\sigma \simeq \partial_y\sigma + s_y\partial_z\sigma$, where s_y is the meridional component of the isopycnal slope. Note that
376 there exists more complex but more accurate computation methods of the neutral slopes and gradi-
377 ents, which are key when the slopes become important^{70,71}. However, in our application the slopes
378 remain weak, with a maximum slope magnitude of 0.08 and a median value of 0.0001.

379 The slope is defined through the horizontal gradients of Absolute Salinity (S_A) and Conser-
380 vative Temperature (Θ), by setting $\partial_{\tilde{x}}\gamma = 0$ and $\partial_{\tilde{y}}\gamma = 0$, such as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} s_x \\ s_y \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{\alpha \nabla \Theta - \beta \nabla S_A}{\alpha \partial_z \Theta - \beta \partial_z S_A}, \quad (9)$$

381 where ∇ is the horizontal gradient, and α and β are the thermal expansion and haline contraction
 382 coefficients, respectively. s^2 is the magnitude of the slope measured through the components inner
 383 product ($=s_x^2+s_y^2$),

384 This epineutral formulation for the gradients allows us to compute an approximation of the
 385 isopycnal diffusion, described in (5) and (7), for any tracer \hat{C} as a function of Cartesian coordinates.

386 This reads:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\hat{C}}^{\text{iso}} \simeq & \partial_z \gamma \left\{ \partial_x \left[\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_x \hat{C} + s_x \partial_z \hat{C} \right) + \frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_y \hat{C} + s_y \partial_z \hat{C} \right) \right] \right. \\ & + s_x \partial_z \left[\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_x \hat{C} + s_x \partial_z \hat{C} \right) + \frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_y \hat{C} + s_y \partial_z \hat{C} \right) \right] \\ & + \partial_y \left[\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_x \hat{C} + s_x \partial_z \hat{C} \right) + \frac{\kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_y \hat{C} + s_y \partial_z \hat{C} \right) \right] \\ & \left. + s_y \partial_z \left[\frac{\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_x \hat{C} + s_x \partial_z \hat{C} \right) + \frac{\kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}}{\partial_z \gamma} \left(\partial_y \hat{C} + s_y \partial_z \hat{C} \right) \right] \right\}. \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

387 This is this formulation, which includes anisotropic, isopycnal diffusivities, that is used in our
 388 study.

389 **Water Mass Transformation Rates.** Building on (10), the action of the isopycnal turbulent term
 390 could be further estimated in terms of transformation rates^{56,72} as:

$$\Psi_{\Theta}^{\#} = \partial_{\gamma} \iint_{\Sigma(\gamma' \leq \gamma)} -\alpha d_{\Theta}^{\text{iso}} d\Sigma \Delta z, \quad (11a)$$

$$\Psi_{S_A}^{\#} = \partial_{\gamma} \iint_{\Sigma(\gamma' \leq \gamma)} \beta d_{S_A}^{\text{iso}} d\Sigma \Delta z, \quad (11b)$$

391

392 where $\Sigma(\gamma' \leq \gamma)$ is the surface of a tracer class below the threshold value γ at 1,000-m
393 depth. Here $\Psi_{\Theta}^{\#}$ and $\Psi_{S_A}^{\#}$ represent neutral density transformations through temperature or salinity
394 changes over a layer of thickness Δz , respectively. These transformations are expressed in Sv,
395 where $1 \text{ Sv} \equiv 10^6 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. In practice, the transformations are estimated using neutral density
396 increment (we chose: $\Delta\gamma=0.03 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$). For consistency, the layer thickness can be estimated
397 though the scaling: $\Delta z \simeq \Delta\gamma(\partial_z\gamma)^{-1}$ (which derives from $d\gamma = \partial_x\gamma dx + \partial_y\gamma dy + \partial_z\gamma dz$). Computation
398 over the globe at 1,000-m depth shows values from 10 m to more than 3,000 m (Supplementary
399 Fig. 1a). In particular the thickness is significantly more important in the Southern Ocean (e.g., the
400 Weddell Sea) and in the subpolar North Atlantic (e.g., Labrador Sea) than in the rest of the globe.
401 However extrapolating our computation over more than 3,000 m is inconsistent with our knowledge
402 of vertical variations of diffusivity coefficient: existence of a steering level^{40,41} and variations with
403 Eddy Kinetic Energy³⁶. Hence we have chosen to restrict the layer thickness amplitude. We have
404 used a uniform layer thickness based on the median value: $\Delta z=70 \text{ m}$ (Supplementary Fig. 1b),
405 regardless of the local stratification ($\partial_z\gamma$). Hence our results, despite being in Sverdrup, only
406 reflects a slice of the ocean at 1 000-m depth.

407 These transformations mathematically expressed a probability density function of density
408 changes induced by cooling/warming or freshening/salinification per neutral density classes, re-
409 spectively. They physically correspond to the volume of water at a given density that is gain-
410 ing/loosing density by cooling/warming or by salinification/freshening, respectively.

411 These transformation rates ($\Psi_{\Theta}^{\#}$ and $\Psi_{S_A}^{\#}$) can be interpreted as the component of the total
 412 transformation induced by isopycnal turbulence. Other components exist²³, such as the one in-
 413 duced by the vertical turbulence⁷³ [$\overline{w'C'}$, visible in (2)] and the small scale diffusion [neglected in
 414 (1), by assuming $Pe \gg 1$].

415 To summarize, (11) shows the existence of transformations when both isopycnal oceanic
 416 turbulence and isopycnal tracer gradients are present (Fig. 2). In this framework, one can compute
 417 transformations associated to temperature and salinity (Fig. 5). The sum of the two transformations
 418 with respect to neutral density classes can also be defined as: $\Psi_{\Theta}^{\#} + \Psi_{S_A}^{\#}$. This sum is expected to
 419 be zero and, therefore, reflects the computation errors (Fig. 5e and f).

420 **Tracer Fields, Diffusivity Data, and Computation Method.** One can compute a tracer transfor-
 421 mation and transformation rates by knowing two properties:

- 422 1. \hat{C} and $\partial_z \hat{C}$ (as well as $\partial_z \gamma$) at all locations [$\forall (x, y)$] along the surface (defined by $z=z_0$,
 423 where z_0 is a constant depth). This can be obtained after assuming $\hat{C} \simeq \bar{C}$ from relevant re-
 424 analyses at any depth, but primarily above the maximum Argo depth sampling of $\sim 2,000$ m
 425 for robustness. In this study, C can be Conservative Temperature or Absolute Salinity
 426 (Fig. 1a-b);
- 427 2. \mathbf{K} at all locations [$\forall (x, y)$] along the same surface (defined by $z=z_0$, where z_0 is a constant
 428 depth), which can be estimated by Argo deep displacements at their parking depth³⁶ (Fig. 1d-
 429 f).

430 Hence the main constraint occur through \mathbf{K} which is only determined at Argo float parking depth
431 (mainly located at $\sim 1,000$ m) and determine the focused depth of our study.

432 We have used the two-dimensional gridded direct estimate of the turbulent anisotropic, isopy-
433 cnal diffusivity coefficients derived from Argo deep displacements³⁶, which are available³⁵ at
434 <https://doi.org/10.17882/91335>, and the global three-dimensional ISAS17 gridded
435 temperature and salinity data derived from objective anaylis of *in situ* observations⁴³ and available
436 at <https://doi.org/10.17882/52367>.

437 The spatially-varying and anisotropic diffusivity coefficients were obtained by reconstruct-
438 ing an analogue turbulent field from deep Argo displacement. This reconstructed turbulent field
439 was used to determine the local dispersion of a locally-injected spike of passive tracer, the rates of
440 dispersion estimating the local diffusivity coefficients along the zonal, meridional, and cross direc-
441 tions. This allows for the full determination of the diffusivity tensor, rather than a single coefficient
442 as often done^{33,34,39}.

443 In practice, after conversion of the data to Conservative Temperature and Absolute Salinity,
444 as well as the computation of neutral density, all the computations are done using $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ cells (i.e.,
445 the native cell of the diffusivity coefficients) on $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid (i.e., the native grid of the diffusiv-
446 ity coefficients). Data are vertically averaged over 40 m bins and vertical levels (needed for the
447 computation of vertical gradients) are separated by 20 m. All conversion to Conservative Temper-
448 ature and Absolute Salinity, as well as computation of neutral density, are done using the Gibbs
449 SeaWater Oceanographic Toolbox of TEOS-10 code.

450 For the water masses framework, we have identified six Water Masses located at the depth of
 451 the study⁴⁹. They are defined through their temperature and salinity range. They are the Mediter-
 452 ranean Water (MW), the Red Sea-Persian Gulf Intermediate Intermediate Water (RSPIGIW), the
 453 Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), the North Atlantic Water (NADW), the Circumpolar Deep
 454 Water (CDW), and the AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW).

455 **Alternative Diffusivity Coefficients.** To test the importance of using spatially-varying and anisotropic
 456 isopycnal diffusivity coefficients we have tested a range of less complex diffusivity coefficients:

457 1. Spatially-uniform and isotropic isopycnal diffusivity coefficients: the diffusivity coefficients
 458 are set to $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}^{\text{Uni \& Iso}} = \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Uni \& Iso}} = (\langle \kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}} \rangle + \langle \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}} \rangle) / 2$ and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Uni \& Iso}} = 0$. These coefficients are applied
 459 to (5).

460 2. Spatially-varying and isotropic isopycnal diffusivity coefficients: the diffusivity coefficients
 461 are set to $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}} = \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}} = (\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}} + \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}) / 2$ and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}} = 0$. These coefficients are applied to
 462 (5).

463 To compare transformations using the different versions of the diffusivity we used a relative
 464 error (RE) using the most complete version as the reference. This reads:

$$\text{RE} = \text{sign} \left[\log \left(\frac{\Psi_{\text{comp}}^{\#}}{\Psi_{\text{ref}}^{\#}} \right) \right] \frac{\text{var} \left(\Psi_{\text{comp}}^{\#} - \Psi_{\text{ref}}^{\#} \right)}{\text{var} \left(\Psi_{\text{ref}}^{\#} \right)}, \quad (12)$$

465 where $\Psi_{\text{ref}}^{\#}$ is the reference transformation (i.e., most complete diffusivity), $\Psi_{\text{comp}}^{\#}$ is the transfor-
 466 mation used for comparison (i.e., less complete diffusivity), and the log term allows to estimate the

467 sign of the mis-estimation (positive and negative for over- and under- estimation, respectively).

468 Additionally to ensure the robustness of our results we have tested two other diffusivity co-
469 efficient datasets. They have been computed using different method and/or different observations.
470 Hence we will also test a modified version of our dataset which is more aligned with the constraints
471 of these two datasets and allows a fairer comparison between the three datasets.

472 a. The first dataset will be named Groeskamp and corresponds to spatially-varying coefficients³⁴.

473 This dataset is available at: [https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Groeskamp_](https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Groeskamp_et_al_2020_-_mixing_diffusivities/12554555)
474 [et_al_2020_-_mixing_diffusivities/12554555](https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Groeskamp_et_al_2020_-_mixing_diffusivities/12554555). The Groeskamp diffusivity
475 coefficients ($\kappa_{\text{Groeskamp}}$) are obtained using a mixing length closure theory to extract cross-
476 flow diffusivity coefficients from salinity ocean observations. These coefficients cover the
477 full depth of the ocean but we extracted their values at 1,000 m (Fig. 6a). Then, to be applied
478 in our framework, we set this single spatially-varying coefficient as spatially-varying but
479 isotropic coefficients: $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}^{\text{Groeskamp}} = \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Groeskamp}} = \kappa_{\text{Groeskamp}}$ and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Groeskamp}} = 0$. Then we apply
480 this set of coefficients to (5).

481 b. The second dataset will be named Roach and also correspond to spatially-varying diffusiv-
482 ity coefficients³⁹. This dataset is available at: [https://github.com/croachutas/](https://github.com/croachutas/Isopycnal_Diffusivity)
483 [Isopycnal_Diffusivity](https://github.com/croachutas/Isopycnal_Diffusivity). The Roach coefficients (κ_{Roach}) use a pairwise distance
484 from deep Argo float displacements to infer the cross-flow diffusivity coefficients. By
485 construction, this dataset is restricted to our 1,000-m studied depth (Fig. 6b). As for the
486 Groeskamp diffusivity coefficients, we set this single spatially-varying coefficient as isotropic

487 spatially-varying coefficients: $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}^{\text{Roach}} = \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Roach}} = \kappa_{\text{Roach}}$ and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Roach}} = 0$. This is applied to (5).

488 c. Since these two sets of diffusion coefficients were computed as cross-flow diffusion coeffi-
489 cients, consistently, we have used our secondary diffusivity coefficient (κ_s) to have a fairer
490 comparison with our diffusivity dataset³⁹. The secondary diffusivity coefficient is the sec-
491 ond eigenvalue of the diffusivity tensor (\mathbf{K}) described in (6). It is by construction weaker
492 than the primary eigenvalue and is more consistent with the cross-flow diffusivity coefficient
493 (i.e., avoiding subgrid stirring and shearing). In principle, this secondary diffusivity is as-
494 sociated with a particular isopycnal direction (i.e., the second eigenvector of the diffusivity
495 tensor). However, here for fair comparison with Groeskamp and Roach diffusivity coeffi-
496 cients described above, we have also applied it as a spatially-varying and isotropic isopycnal
497 diffusivity coefficients. Hence, it is set as: $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}^{\text{sec}}} = \kappa_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}^{\text{sec}}} = \kappa_s$ and $\kappa_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}^{\text{Var \& Iso}^{\text{sec}}} = 0$.
498 These coefficients are applied to (5).

499 Finally for comparison purpose, we have computed the diapycnal transformation as a vertical
500 diffusion: $d_C^{\text{dia}} = \partial_z(\kappa_z \partial_z \hat{C})$, where κ_z is the vertical diffusivity coefficient. We have used spatially-
501 varying diffusivity coefficients^{59,60} available at <https://doi.org/10.17882/73082>, and
502 have extracted the corresponding values for 1,000-m depth (Supplementary Fig. 2). This shows
503 the expected topographic control of the vertical diffusion coefficients.

504 **Data availability** The global gridded temperature and salinity product is ISAS17 (release key: 86441)
505 and available at: <https://doi.org/10.17882/52367>. Turbulent anisotropic, isopycnal diffusiv-
506 ity coefficients derived from ANDRO Argo deep displacements are available at <https://doi.org/>

507 10.17882/91335. ISAS and ANDRO Argo floats displacements products are made available by SNO
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509 IUEM/CNRS/INSU), and was funded by Ifremer, Coriolis, SOERE-CTDO2, SNO Argo France, and CPER
510 Bretagne Obsocan. Groeskamp isopycnal diffusivity coefficients are available at https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Groeskamp_et_al_2020_-_mixing_diffusivities/12554555.
511 Roach isopycnal diffusivity coefficients are available at https://github.com/croachutas/Isopycnal_Diffusivity. Vertical diffusivity coefficients are available at: <https://doi.org/10.17882/73082>.

515 **Code availability** The Gibbs SeaWater Oceanographic Toolbox of TEOS-10 package used for the compu-
516 tation of Neutral Density, Absolute Salinity, and Conservative Temperature is available at http://www.teos-10.org/pubs/gsw/html/gsw_contents.html. The M_Map package for MATLAB used
517 for global mapping of data is available online at <https://www-old.eoas.ubc.ca/~rich/map.html>. The code developed for the analyses and for producing the figures are available from the correspond-
518 ing author on request.

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696 and the writing of the manuscript. FS initiated the analysis and developed the data analysis.

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698 **Figure 1 Climatological tracer fields and horizontal diffusivity at 1,000-m depth.** (a) Con-
699 servative Temperature, (b) Absolute Salinity, and (c) neutral density at 1,000-m depth
700 from the climatological-annual mean of gridded ISAS17 product⁴³. (d) Primary and (e)
701 secondary diffusivity, as well as their respective directions, estimated from deep Argo dis-
702 placements at 1,000-m depth from the ANDRO dataset³⁶. (f) Six Water Masses are identi-
703 fied at 1,000-m depth⁴⁹ and denoted through color patches. These Water Masses are the
704 Mediterranean Water (MW), the Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW),
705 the AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), the
706 Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and the AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW). Four key re-
707 gions are also highlighted and used in the rest of the study : North Atlantic (NA), Atlantic
708 sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I), and Pacific
709 sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P).

710 **Figure 2 Distribution of temperature and salinity along 25°E and potential transforma-**
711 **tion induced by the oceanic isopycnal turbulence.** (a) Conservative Temperature and (b)
712 Absolute Salinity along 25°W from the climatological-annual mean of gridded ISAS17
713 product⁴³. The light grey lines indicates neutral density contour of 26.5, 27.25, 27.85, and
714 28.02 kg m⁻³. Because existence of Temperature and Salinity (TS) gradients along isopy-
715 cnal, the oceanic isopycnal turbulent diffusion (grey arrow) can transform TS-properties
716 (black spiral). This is especially true at 1 000-m depth (denoted by the horizontal black
717 line) where isopycnal temperature and salinity gradients are important given the range

718 of different Water Masses. At 25°E we have: AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW), AntArc-
719 tic Intermediate Water (AAIW), Mediterranean Water (MW), North Atlantic Deep Water
720 (NADW), and Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW). As suggested by the schematic (a and b),
721 it is possible to compute the rates of change, following (10), and the corresponding water
722 mass transformation, following (11), associated to a tracer (e.g., temperature or salinity).

723 **Figure 3 Temperature rates of change at 1,000-m depth.** Rates of Change in (a) Conser-
724 vative Temperature at 1,000-m depth induced by the isopycnal turbulence. Inset show the
725 same rates of change but as a Temperature-Salinity diagram, with neutral density in con-
726 tours (in kg m^{-3} with intervals of 0.2 kg m^{-3}). (b-e) same as the inset but for regional es-
727 timations of the rates of change for Conservative Temperature. The four selected regions
728 are North Atlantic (NA), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of South-
729 ern Ocean (SO-I), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P), as separated by the lines
730 and represented in Fig. 1f. In the scatter plots, the values are ordered in absolute rates
731 of change (potentially hiding weaker rates of change of the same Temperature-Salinity
732 class). The color patches show properties of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean
733 Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermedi-
734 ate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW),
735 and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW).

736 **Figure 4 Salinity rates of change at 1,000-m depth.** Rates of Change in (a) Absolute Salin-
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738 change but as a Temperature-Salinity diagram, with neutral density in contours (in kg m^{-3}
739 with intervals of 0.2 kg m^{-3}). (b-e) same as the inset but for regional estimations of the
740 rates of change for Absolute Salinity. The four selected regions are North Atlantic (NA),
741 Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I), and
742 Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P), as separated by the lines and represented in
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746 Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW),
747 North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bot-
748 tom Water (AABW).

749 **Figure 5 Temperature and Salinity water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for den-**
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752 density classes. Positive or negative values show warming or salinification and cooling
753 or freshening, respectively. (a, c, and e) Red and blue bars show positive and negative
754 transformations for the anisotropic and spatially-varying diffusivity, respectively; dark and
755 light grey bars show transformations for the isotropic and spatially-varying and for the
756 isotropic and for the globally-uniform diffusivity (set as the local-mean and global-mean of
757 the anisotropic diffusivity), respectively. The cyan lines are the transformations induced
758 by diapycnal diffusion. (e, d, and f) The transformations are split in geographical sectors:

759 global (black lines), North Atlantic (NA, orange line), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean
760 (SO-A, blue line), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I, yellow line), and Pacific sec-
761 tor of Southern Ocean (SO-P, green line), as represented in Fig. 1f. The curves have
762 been smoothed using a moving average window of 0.06 kg m^{-3} and re-interpolated on
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766 North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bot-
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768 salinity transformations correspond to the computational error.

769 **Figure 6 Other estimations of isopycnal diffusivity and induced Temperature and Salinity**
770 **water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for density class.** (a and b) Isopycnal diffusivity
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772 and Roach, respectively). Water mass transformations in term of density changes for
773 (c) Conservative Temperature and for (d) Absolute Salinity for density classes. Blue
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775 dashed blue lines show results for the average between primary and secondary diffusiv-
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Turbulent Isopycnal Mixing dominates Thermohaline
Transformations of Intermediate Ocean Waters

FLORIAN SÉVELLEC, NICOLAS KOŁODZIEJCZYK, AND ESTHER PORTELA

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- 3 **Temperature rate of changes at 1,000-m depth.** Rate of Changes in (a) Conservative Temperature at 1,000-m depth induced by the isopycnal turbulence. Inset show the same rate of changes but as a Temperature-Salinity diagram, with neutral density in contours (in kg m⁻³ with intervals of 0.2 kg m⁻³). (b-e) same as the inset but for regional estimations of the rate of changes for Conservative Temperature. The four selected regions are North Atlantic (NA), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P), as separated by the lines and represented in Fig. 1f. In the scatter plots, the values are ordered in absolute rate of changes (potentially hiding weaker rate of changes of the same Temperature-Salinity class). The color patches show properties of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW). 6

- 4 **Salinity rate of changes at 1,000-m depth.** Rate of Changes in (a) Absolute Salinity at 1,000-m depth induced by the isopycnal turbulence. Inset show the same rate of changes but as a Temperature-Salinity diagram, with neutral density in contours (in kg m^{-3} with intervals of 0.2 kg m^{-3}). (b-e) same as the inset but for regional estimations of the rate of changes for Absolute Salinity. The four selected regions are North Atlantic (NA), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P), as separated by the lines and represented in Fig. 1f. In the scatter plots, the values are ordered in absolute rate of changes (potentially hiding weaker rate of changes of the same Temperature-Salinity class). The color patches show properties of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW). . . .
- 5 **Temperature and Salinity water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for density classes.** Water mass transformations in term of density changes for (a and b) Conservative Temperature and for (b and d) Absolute Salinity, and (c and d) their sum for density classes. Positive or negative values show warming or salinification and cooling or freshening, respectively. (a, c, and e) Red and blue bars show positive and negative transformations for the anisotropic and spatially-varying diffusivity, respectively; dark and light grey bars show transformations for the isotropic and spatially-varying and for the isotropic and for the globally-uniform diffusivity (set as the local-mean and global-mean of the anisotropic diffusivity), respectively. The cyan lines are the transformations induced by diapycnal diffusion. (e, d, and f) The transformations are split in geographical sectors: global (black lines), North Atlantic (NA, orange line), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A, blue line), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I, yellow line), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P, green line), as represented in Fig. 1f. The curves have been smoothed using a moving average window of 0.06 kg m^{-3} and re-interpolated on regular 0.012 kg m^{-3} grid with a spline interpolation. The horizontal color patches show neutral density classes of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW). (e and f) Non-zero values for the sum of isopycnal temperature and salinity transformations correspond to the computational error. . . .

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6 **Other estimations of isopycnal diffusivity and induced Temperature and Salinity water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for density classes.** (a and b) Isopycnal diffusivity coefficients at 1,000-m estimated with alternative methods^{34,39} (denoted as Groeskamp and Roach, respectively). Water mass transformations in term of density changes for (c) Conservative Temperature and for (d) Absolute Salinity for density classes. Blue lines show transformations for the isotropic and spatially-varying diffusivity. Solid and dashed blue lines show results for the average between primary and secondary diffusivities and secondary diffusivities, respectively. The former is strictly identical to the dark grey bars of Fig. 5. Orange and red lines show transformations for the Groeskamp and Roach diffusivities, respectively. The curves have been smoothed using a moving average window of 0.06 kg m^{-3} re-interpolated on regular 0.012 kg m^{-3} grid with a spline interpolation. The horizontal color patches show neutral density classes of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW).

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FIGURE 4: **Salinity rate of changes at 1,000-m depth.** Rate of Changes in (a) Absolute Salinity at 1,000-m depth induced by the isopycnal turbulence. Inset show the same rate of changes but as a Temperature-Salinity diagram, with neutral density in contours (in kg m^{-3} with intervals of 0.2 kg m^{-3}). (b-e) same as the inset but for regional estimations of the rate of changes for Absolute Salinity. The four selected regions are North Atlantic (NA), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P), as separated by the lines and represented in Fig. 1f. In the scatter plots, the values are ordered in absolute rate of changes (potentially hiding weaker rate of changes of the same Temperature-Salinity class). The color patches show properties of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea-Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW).

FIGURE 5: **Temperature and Salinity water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for density classes.** Water mass transformations in term of density changes for (a and b) Conservative Temperature and for (b and d) Absolute Salinity, and (c and d) their sum for density classes. Positive or negative values show warming or salinification and cooling or freshening, respectively. (a, c, and e) Red and blue bars show positive and negative transformations for the anisotropic and spatially-varying diffusivity, respectively; dark and light grey bars show transformations for the isotropic and spatially-varying and for the isotropic and for the globally-uniform diffusivity (set as the local-mean and global-mean of the anisotropic diffusivity), respectively. The cyan lines are the transformations induced by diapycnal diffusion. (e, d, and f) The transformations are split in geographical sectors: global (black lines), North Atlantic (NA, orange line), Atlantic sector of Southern Ocean (SO-A, blue line), Indian sector of Southern Ocean (SO-I, yellow line), and Pacific sector of Southern Ocean (SO-P, green line), as represented in Fig. 1f. The curves have been smoothed using a moving average window of 0.06 kg m^{-3} and re-interpolated on regular 0.012 kg m^{-3} grid with a spline interpolation. The horizontal color patches show neutral density classes of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW). (e and f) Non-zero values for the sum of isopycnal temperature and salinity transformations correspond to the computational error.

FIGURE 6: **Other estimations of isopycnal diffusivity and induced Temperature and Salinity water mass transformations at 1,000-m depth for density classes.** (a and b) Isopycnal diffusivity coefficients at 1,000-m estimated with alternative methods^{34,39} (denoted as Groeskamp and Roach, respectively). Water mass transformations in term of density changes for (c) Conservative Temperature and for (d) Absolute Salinity for density classes. Blue lines show transformations for the isotropic and spatially-varying diffusivity. Solid and dashed blue lines show results for the average between primary and secondary diffusivities and secondary diffusivities, respectively. The former is strictly identical to the dark grey bars of Fig. 5. Orange and red lines show transformations for the Groeskamp and Roach diffusivities, respectively. The curves have been smoothed using a moving average window of 0.06 kg m^{-3} re-interpolated on regular 0.012 kg m^{-3} grid with a spline interpolation. The horizontal color patches show neutral density classes of selected Water Masses⁴⁹: Mediterranean Water (MW), Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW).

Turbulent Isopycnal Mixing dominates Thermohaline
Transformations of Intermediate Ocean Waters

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Supplementary Information

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1: **Vertical layer thickness estimated for a density increment of 0.03 kg m^{-3} based on local stratification.** (a and b) Map and distribution of thickness, respectively. The median value is 68 m. Hence we have used $\Delta z=70 \text{ m}$ in (11) as a scaling of the vertical layer thickness in our estimated transformations.

LOG₁₀ OF VERTICAL DIFFUSIVITY

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2: **Vertical diffusivity at 1,000-m depth.** Vertical diffusivity coefficients^{59,60} at 1,000-m used to assess the temperature and salinity diapycnal transformations.